

ESTIMATE THE MARKETING COST, MARKETING EFFICIENCY, MARKETING MARGIN AND PRODUCER'S SHARE OF POTATO MARKETING CHANNELS OF POTATO IN PURNEA DISTRICT, BIHAR.

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Abstract:

Potatoes are an important food and cash crop grown in many countries, including India. The researchers conducted a study on potato production and marketing in the Purnea district of Bihar. In the study randomly sampled 120 farmers from selected villages, with varying sizes of landholdings. Potatoes are categorized by size, color, quality, and variety for marketing purposes, and are transported in large nets via trucks. Marketing costs were highest for Channel 2 (Rs. 490/qt), followed by Channel 3 and Channel 1 (Rs. 345/qt and Rs. 150/qt, respectively). Channel 3 had the highest marketing margin (Rs. 750/qt). Marketing efficiency was highest for Channel 1 (10.38%), followed by Channel 2 and Channel 3 (2.16% and 2.69%, respectively). The producer's share was highest for Channel 1 (90.37%), followed by Channel 2 and Channel 3 (55.52% and 44.37%, respectively). The study identified a lack of awareness about potato market prices as a major challenge for potato growers in the area.

Keywords: cost of marketing, marketing channel, marketing efficiency, marketing margin

Introduction:

Potatoes are a significant crop grown in over 100 countries, with India ranking third in potato cultivation and second in production after China (Borah et al. 2016). Potato marketing in India is complex and involves multiple channels and stakeholders, with farmers typically selling to intermediaries who sell to wholesalers or retailers. The marketing of potatoes in Bihar is largely unorganized and in the hands of private trade, with producers usually marketing potatoes as vegetables. The Indian government has implemented policies such as subsidies for storage and transportation infrastructure and market yards to support potato marketing, most efficient one due to direct sale of the produce. The study suggested that modern market infrastructure may be built up with public-private partnership to bring efficiency in marketing of potato. Despite the challenges, there are opportunities for farmers to improve their profitability through better storage and marketing practice (Kaur and Sidhu 2015).

Research Methodology:

Selection of the district: In order to study "Production and Marketing of Potato" the present study was undertaken in Purnia district of Bihar. The district was purposively selected because this district had abundant Potato production.

Selection of block: Purnea district have total 14 blocks, among which Purnea East block was selected for study due to the Farmer's land holding capacity and its high production of potato.

Selection of Villages: There 5 % villages were selected randomly Out of 77 villages, Namely Harda, Ranipatra, Barsauni, Rampur, Gangaili Bazar.

Selection of market and Marketing functionaries: -

Channels-1: Producer → consumer

Channels-2: Producer → Wholesaler → Retailer → consumers

Channels -3: Producer → Village Trader → wholesaler → retailer consumers

Marketing Cost:

The total cost, incurred on marketing either in cash or in kind by the producer seller and by the various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of the commodity reaches the ultimate consumer.

$$C = CF + CM_1 + CM_2 + CM_3 + \dots + CM_n$$

Where, C = Total cost of marketing of commodity

CF = Cost paid by the producer from the time of produce leave farm till he sale it.

CMI = Cost incurred by the i^{th} middleman in the process of buying and selling the product.**Marketing Efficiency:**

It was calculated using Acharya's Modified Marketing efficiency as follows-

$$MME = \frac{FP}{MC + MM}$$

Where, MME is modified measure of marketing efficiency.

FP = Price received by farmers; MC = Marketing cost; MM = Marketing margin

Producer Share in Consumer Rupee:

It is the price received by the farmer expressed as a percentage of the retail price.

$$PS = \frac{PF \times 100}{PR}$$

Where, PF = Price received by the farmer; PR = Retail price (consumer price)

Results and Discussion:

Estimate the marketing cost, marketing efficiency, marketing margin and Producer's share of Potato marketing channels.

Marketing Channel Of Potato

The different channels through which potato flows from the point of production till it reaches the consumers were identified and the same were categorized into the following three channels:

Table:1 Channel-1

Description	Rs. /Qt	%
1. Producer sale price(avg.)	1108.33	69.77
1.1. Transportation cost	50	3.14
1.2. Packaging cost	20	1.25
1.3. Storage cost	50	3.14
1.4. Miscellaneous cost	30	1.88
1.5. Total wastage Cost	150	9.44
2. Net price received by producer	1408.33	88.66
3. Total Marketing Cost	150	9.44
4. Consumer paid price	1558.33	100
5. Marketing Efficiency (%)	10.38	-

6. Producer's Share (PS=PP/CR*100)**90.37**

The channel I has one intermediary producer to consumer here the producer picks up potato and sell it to consumer hand to hand the transportation cost, packaging cost, storage cost is very less as compare to other two channel. The total marketing cost is Rs.150/qt, Consumer paid price is Rs.1558.33/qt and marketing efficiency is 25.33%.

Table: 2- Channel-2

Description	(Rs. /Qt)	%
A. Producer sale price to wholesaler		
1. Charges paid by producer	200	15.28
2. Net price received by producer	1108.33	84.71
3. Producer selling price	1308.33	100
B. Cost incurred by wholesaler		
1. Wholesaler buying price	1308.33	89.22
2. Transportation /Storage	50	3.40
3. Loading and Unloading Charges	50	3.40
4. Market fees (@ 2%)	28	1.90
5. Net price paid by wholesaler	1466.33	100
6. Wholesaler marketing cost	160	8.30
7. Wholesaler selling	300	15.57
C. Cost incurred by retailer	1926.33	100
1. Retailer paid price	1926.33	81.76
2. Loading and Unloading Charges	40	1.69
3. Storage cost /Transportation cost	50	2.12
4. Container	30	1.27
5. Miscellaneous cost	10	0.42
6. Retailer marketing Cost	130	-
7. Retailer marketing Margins	300	12.73
8. Retailer Selling Price	2356.33	100
D. Total marketing Cost(A1+B6+C6)	490	-
E. Total marketing Margins(B7+C7)	600	-
F. Marketing Cost+ Marketing Margins	1090	
F. Marketing Efficiency (%)	2.16	-
G. Producer's Share (PS=PP/CR*100)	55.52	

The channel II study shows that the total marketing cost for this channel is Rs. 490/qt, with a total marketing margin of Rs. 700/qt, and a marketing efficiency of 2.16%. These costs include transportation, storage, and other miscellaneous expenses that add up for the wholesaler and retailer who purchase from the producer and then sell to the consumer.

Table 3.3 Channel-3

Description	(Rs./qt)	%
A. 1. Producer sale price to traders		
2. Cost incurred by Producer	-	-
3. Total marketing cost	-	-
4. Net price received by Producer	1308.33	-
B. Cost incurred by traders		
1. Traders buying price	1308.33	72.35
2. Transportation	85	4.70
3. Loading and Unloading Charges	60	3.31
4. Packaging Charges	55	3.04
5. Market fees	50	2.76
6. Total Marketing Cost of traders	100	5.52
7. Marketing Margin of traders	150	8.29
8. Traders Selling Price	1808.33	100
C. Cost incurred by wholesaler		
1. Wholesaler buying price	1808.33	76.67
2. Transportation	-	-
3. Loading and Unloading	40	1.69
4. Market fees	35	1.48
5. Storage cost	50	2.12
6. Wholesaler Marketing Cost	125	5.30

7. Wholesaler Marketing Margins	300	12.72
8. Wholeseller Selling Price	2358.33	100
D. Cost incurred by retailer	2358.33	79.98
1. Transportation	60	2.03
2. Loading and Unloading	30	1.01
3. Storage Cost	-	-
4. Cleaning	-	-
5. Containers	40	1.35
6. Market fees	40	1.35
7. Marketing Cost of retailer	120	4.07
8. Marketing Margins of retailers	300	10.17
9. Retailer Selling Price	2948.33	100
E. Total Marketing Cost(B6+C6+D7)	345	-
F. Total Marketing Margins(B7+C7+D8)	750	-
G. Marketing Cost+ Marketing Margins	1095	
H. Marketing Efficiency (%)	2.69	-
I. Producer's Share (PS=PP/CR*100)	44.37	

The channel III has 3 intermediaries Producer to Village Contractor to wholesaler to retailer to consumer. Here, best quality of potato export from one state to another so transportation cost, storage cost and miscellaneous cost is high as compared to other two channel. The total marketing cost is Rs.345/qt, marketing margins is Rs.750/qt and marketing efficiency is 2.69.

Conclusion:

The study focused on the production and marketing of potatoes in Purnia district, Bihar, India, evaluating three channels of potato marketing based on marketing cost, marketing efficiency, marketing margin, and producer's share in consumer rupee. The three channels evaluated were: (1) Direct sale from the producer to the consumer. (2) Sale from the producer to the wholesaler, then to the retailer, and finally to the consumer. (3) Sale from the producer to the village trader, then to the wholesaler, retailer, and finally to the consumer.

The study found that Channel 1 provides the highest producer's share in consumer rupee and the lowest marketing cost and marketing efficiency. Channel 2 has higher marketing costs and lower producer's share in consumer rupee compared to Channel 1, but lower marketing costs and higher producer's share compared to Channel 3. Channel 3 has the highest marketing costs and the lowest producer's share in consumer rupee. The study concludes that there is a need to improve marketing efficiency and reduce marketing costs for the benefit of potato producers and consumers in Bihar state.

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